

**A STUDY OF THE USE OF INTERNET AND SOCIAL MEDIA BY
STAKEHOLDERS OF PRE SERVICE TEACHER EDUCATION AND
ITS EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS**

DR. SURESH G. ISAVE

Associate Professor, Tilak College of Education, Pune

Abstract

The paper is about the use of internet and social media by various stakeholders of B.Ed. course including principal, educators and students to understand the status of use ICT in teacher education. Findings of the study are useful to decide the learning experiences for student-teachers. Also useful to make policy and execution of ICT integration in teacher education. As we know that most of stakeholders using internet and social media, but we need to know what exact status of it. So the evidences are collected and its educational implications are discussed in the paper.

Keywords – *teacher education, ICT, social media, educational technology, stakeholders of education*

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1. Introduction:

ICT has become integrated part of education. Teachers are supposed to be techno savvy. Teacher education curriculum is also integrating ICT component. There are many tools of ICT which can be used in education. Pre service teacher education is key of all the changes. If ICT is well implemented in teacher education, teachers will be well prepared for use of ICT tools in education. So teacher education should be well prepared for integration of ICT in education. It can be observed that social media has been used lot by people including stakeholders of teacher education. Social media is one of the prominent communication tool nowadays even for official communication. Student-teachers make use of internet and smart phone. Use of ICT and Social media in education.

2. Significance of the study:

It is useful to find out the use of ICT by various stakeholders to see how well per service teacher educators are prepared for integration of ICT. If all stake holders' of education use ICT, it can be used at ease in teacher education. Instead of anticipating the use ICT enablement of stakeholders, the group report is essential to prepare plan and policy of use of ICT in teacher education. It would be useful to understand status of availability of ICT resources which is useful to frame curriculum, to decide learning experiences and to determine learning strategies for teacher education.

3. Objectives –

1. To find out nature of the use of internet and its educational implications.
2. To find out nature of the use of social media and its educational implications.
3. To find out nature of the use of mobile apps and its educational implications.

4. Operational definitions:

- i) Use of Internet – The use of internet is with reference to devices, time spent and data consumption.
- ii) Social Media – WhatsApp & Face book have been considered as a social media for the present study.
- iii) Pre service teacher education –Two years B.Ed. program designed and implemented in Maharashtra state of India in the academic year 2018-19
- iv) Stakeholders – Principal, teacher-educators and students are referred here as a stakeholders of pre service teacher education.
- v) Educational Implications – Implication in policy making, curriculum designing and learning resources development.

5. Scope –

The findings of the study are applicable to stakeholders B.Ed. course during academic year 2018-19 in Pune, India.

6. Sampling –

The sample of informants amongst the stakeholders was selected by lottery technique of random sampling. 42 informants responded to the data collection tool.

7. Data collection tool –

The online questionnaire was developed by the researcher by using Google form. The questionnaire consists of 10 questions which were close ended.

8. Data Collection –

The researcher selected 10 colleges by random sampling and the link of the Google form was shared with principal on WhatsApp. Then principals shared this link to their respective college's WhatsApp group and they filled the questionnaire. Informants from 4 colleges responded to the questionnaire.

9. Data analysis–

The questionnaire had 10 close ended questions distributed through google form. These questions are analyzed in percentage.

Q1.Select the name of your college?

Figure 1: Name of the college

Interpretation: Most responses are from Arihant College of Education, Pune, Tilak College of Education, Pune and Navjeevan College of Education, Neral

Q2. What is your age group?

Figure 2: Age groups of stakeholders

Interpretation: Age group of 20 to 35 is more techno savvy.

Educational Implications: These respondents are teacher educators and student teachers, they are techno savvy. They can competent to create, share, and use various online resources.

Q3. Select your role in teacher education.

Figure 3: Stakeholder

Observation: The stakeholders in the sample were distributed like Principals -04, teacher-educators 11 and student-teachers -27.

Q4. On which device you access internet?

Figure 4: Devices used to access internet

Interpretation: Most of the stakeholders use smart phone as a device to use internet.

Educational Implications: Mainly, smart phone should be used as an ICT tool in teacher education program. Smart phones are generally always with users, so it can be used for faster communication. This platform should be utilized to create and share e-resources e.g. demo lessons of various skills.

Q5. How much you required daily?

Figure 5: Daily data used by stakeholders

Interpretation: Most of stakeholders need at least 1GB data daily.

Educational Implications: Most of stakeholders need atleast 1GB per day. Educational resources can be even provided in the form of video. Many learning resources can be made available for student teachers because they can afford data.

Q6. What is the purpose of the use of internet?

Figure 6: Purpose of the use of internet

Interpretation: Stakeholder make use of internet for educational, social media, communication, entertainment and gaming.

Educational Implication: Stakeholders uses mobile for education purpose, so teacher education can be designed with blended learning mode. They use social media too, so this platform can be used to create educational groups which can be used to communicate and to share learning resources too.

Q7. How much time you spend daily on internet?

Figure 7: Daily time spent online by stakeholders

Interpretation: Majority of stakeholders spend one to three hours daily.

Educational Implication: The time spent online by stakeholders are important point in e-learning mode. So, when planning online course or blended learning course daily online activity can be given. It also gives scope to organize webinar.

Q8. Which social media platform do you use?

Figure 8 : Use of different social media platforms by stakeholders

Interpretation: All stakeholders active various social media platform like WhatsApp, Face book and YouTube.

Educational Implications: Since WhatsApp and Face book are mostly used social media platform those can be used for sharing and communication. In addition to this YouTube can be used too. Online videos channel can be created on YouTube for educational purpose.

Q9. What types of Apps are there in your mobile phone?

Figure 9 :Types of apps in stakeholders’ smart phone

Interpretation: Majority of stakeholders having social media app and educational apps.

Educational Implications: Since many stakeholders using educational mobile apps, some apps related to teacher education can be developed which is useful to create educational resources and share it.

10. Findings –

1. Most of stakeholders use internet for education purpose, so it is possible to make use of internet for educational purpose in teacher education.
2. Most of stakeholders of teacher education use WhatsApp and Facebook apps, so these social media apps can be used for to share educational resources.
3. Most of stakeholders use educational and social media apps in their smart phones, so theses platforms can be used for educational utilization.

11. Discussion of the findings:

Since it’s always assumed that ICT is useful for everyone and they are techno savvy. This study was conducted in colleges in urban area which shows that most of stakeholders of teacher education i.e. Principal, teacher-educator, student-teacher are techno savvy and using

internet, social media and mobile apps. The study also shows that these stakeholders spend daily time on internet and consuming good amount of data. So, Internet, Social media, You Tube and Mobile Apps such online platforms should be used for educational purpose. Since majority of them use internet on smart phones they are having nearest reach to internet. So many educational resources can be created which they can access anytime. These positive findings should be considered in policy making and implementation of teacher education.

13. Conclusion:

Majority of stakeholders of teacher education use smart phone, internet, social media and mobile apps, hence it can be concluded that ICT can be integrated positively in teacher education.

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